

Genetic mapping of agronomically important traits in einkorn wheat

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Supplementary Data 2: The distribution of phenotypic data for the DV92×G3116 RIL population of einkorn wheat

The Shapiro-Wilk test was performed to assess the normality of the phenotypic data collected for the DV92×G3116 RIL population in up to eight seasons (Supplementary Table S4).

The analysis for each trait was repeated twice, with **(part A of this supplementary file)** and without outliers **(part B)**, to compare the accuracy of testing. Outliers were detected using the interquartile range (IQR) leading to the removal of phenotypic values outside 1.5 times the IQR between the first and third quartiles.

The resulting p-values are presented in graphs along with distribution and Q-Q plots after testing the null hypothesis. Red color means that the traits do not follow a normal distribution.

Part A: Analysis with outliers

plant_architecture_8
p-value: 1e-04

leaf_pubescence_1
p-value: 0

leaf_pubescence_2
p-value: 0

leaf_pubescence_3
p-value: 0

leaf_pubescence_4
p-value: 0

leaf_pubescence_5
p-value: 0

leaf_pubescence_6
p-value: 0

leaf_pubescence_7
p-value: 0

leaf_pubescence_8
p-value: 0

rachis_brittleness_5
p-value: 0

rachis_brittleness_6
p-value: 1e-04

rachis_brittleness_7
p-value: 0

n_of_grains_spikelet_3
p-value: 0.0012

n_of_grains_spikelet_4
p-value: 0.4132

n_of_grains_spikelet_5
p-value: 0.0266

n_of_grains_spikelet_6
p-value: 0.0092

n_of_grains_spikelet_7
p-value: 0.2542

n_of_grains_spikelet_8
p-value: 0.0055

grain_thickness_1in1_4
p-value: 0.0036

grain_thickness_1in1_5
p-value: 0.0123

grain_thickness_1in1_6
p-value: 0.0092

grain_thickness_1in1_7
p-value: 0.0085

grain_thickness_1in1_8
p-value: 0.08

grain_thickness_2in1_3
p-value: 0.1541

grain_thickness_2in1_4
p-value: 0.3006

grain_thickness_2in1_5
p-value: 0.0953

grain_thickness_2in1_6
p-value: 0.2947

Part B: Analysis without outliers

rachis_brittleness_5
p-value: 0

rachis_brittleness_6
p-value: 1e-04

rachis_brittleness_7
p-value: 0

n_of_grains_spikelet_3
p-value: 0.0644

n_of_grains_spikelet_4
p-value: 0.4132

n_of_grains_spikelet_5
p-value: 0.0439

n_of_grains_spikelet_6
p-value: 0.1731

n_of_grains_spikelet_7
p-value: 0.5085

n_of_grains_spikelet_8
p-value: 0.6189

